

PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

Scientific and technical journal

e-ISSN: 2901-7845 (ISSN: 2091-5004)

2025, VOLUME-03, ISSUE-04.

The journal is included in the list of scientific journals in which scientific articles on technical sciences (construction, mechanics and machine building) and architecture are subject to publication by the decision of the OAK Board (certificate No. 00757. 2000.31.01). It is hereby notified that the articles published in English in our journal are equated to scientific articles published in foreign scientific publications in accordance with the decision of the OAK

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MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF
UZBEKISTAN

Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

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ПРОБЛЕМЫ АРХИТЕКТУРЫ И СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА
(научно-технический журнал) 2025, ТОМ 3, ВЫПУСК 45383.

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, 2025, 3-JILD, 4-SON,

ISSN: 2091-5004, e-ISSN:2901-7845
<https://portal.issn.org/resource/ISSN/2091-5004>

Samarkand, 2025

TYOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PUBLIC SERVICE CENTER BUILDING IN MINNEAPOLIS, NORTH AMERICA.

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Abstract: This article examines the architectural and functional typology of the Public Service Center building located in Minneapolis, USA. The role of the building in administrative, public, and service functions, architectural solutions, its connection with urban infrastructure, and integration with modern technologies are analyzed.

Keywords: Public services, building typology, modernism, urban infrastructure, public buildings, Minneapolis, interior, building floor plan, design, project construction, problems, advantages, building codes, master plan planning solutions.

The project began in 2017 with the construction of a new Civil Service Building near the Minneapolis City Hall, which will update the city's critical systems and operations and give the civil service a modern look. Aluminum and glass materials were used in the facade of the skyscraper. (Fig. 1)

Figure 1 Building of the Public Service Center in Minneapolis, North America

The convenience of entering the building will help attract the population, and nearby bus and light rail stations will serve citizens visiting the building. The large special staircase in the entrance foyer is a huge public space visually associated with street life. The first and second floors of the building are designed as a public service center. The building also has office floors. From the third floor to the 10th floor, 10 city departments and more than 1,200 city employees are

concentrated in one building. After dispersing to various buildings, employees will be provided with daytime illuminated workplaces, quiet spaces for personal time, improved air quality, and a conference area, cafe, and terrace on the top floor.

On the first floor of the building, there is an entrance information room, a conference hall, staff rooms, warehouses, and service rooms. The main service halls are located on the second floor. Since the building is multi-story, elevators and the aforementioned rooms are located on the first floor. (Fig. 2)

Figure 2 Plan of the first floor of the Public Service Center building in Minneapolis, North America

The second floor of the building houses halls for providing public services, waiting areas, staff rooms, the director's office, elevators, and stairs. The building is designed to serve the population of a very large city. (Fig. 3)

Figure 3 Plan of the second floor of the Public Service Center building in Minneapolis, North America

In the state building, which requires enhanced security, the design still supports an open and airy environment. The concept of the building is not prioritized over the needs of employees, there are spaces for collective and individual work. Due to the openness of all floors and stairwells of the building, light penetrates deeply into its interior, which brings employees even closer to the outdoors. (Fig. 4)

Figure 4 Interior view of the Public Service Center building in Minneapolis, North America

During the analysis of the master plan of the Public Services Center building, taking into account the location of a railway station next to the building, a large open area was designed in front of the building. A large fountain has been designed in the square for the population and to improve the public climate. (Fig. 5)

Figure 5. General plan of the Public Service Center building in Minneapolis, North America.

A typological analysis of this building was carried out, and the following was established.

1. Typological position and functional structure

Typology: Public Service Center - this is a type of public building. The building includes several functional zones: administrative, service, and public spaces.

Floor distribution: The floors of the building are functionally clearly separated. Public services are located on the lower floors (1-2 floors), while administrative and office departments are located on the upper floors.

This functional separation contributes to the effective functioning of the building.

Workplaces and recreation areas: The presence of recreation areas for employees, conferences, cafes, and terraces on the upper floors, along with workplaces, architecturally humanizes the internal environment.

2. Architectural forms and materials

Figure: The skyscraper is located in a vertical composition, in the center of the city, therefore it is developed upwards. This ensures the dominance of the appearance on the city square.

Materials: Aluminum and glass coatings are modern, lightweight materials that allow for deep penetration of light. The glass facade provides a large degree of openness to the building and natural lighting to the interior space.

Aesthetics: Minimalist modernist style building, clean lines, simplified shapes, and contrasting materials.

3. Interior and design

Open space concept: Stairs and foyers are arranged in large volumes and in open spaces, which strengthens the visual connection between inner and outer space.

Natural lighting: Deep light penetration into the building creates a comfortable working environment for employees and clients, reduces stress, and increases efficiency.

4. Integration into the urban environment

Transport infrastructure: The proximity of the building to bus and light rail stations corresponds to the city's infrastructure, creating conveniences for the population.

Public space: The presence of a large open space and a fountain in front of the building makes this area an important place for the public climate, positively influencing the life of the city.

Visual connection: the strengthening of visual communication from the foyer to the street and vice versa - provides organic integration between the urban space and the interior space of the building.

5. Technologies and environmental solutions

Modern technologies: Elevators, enhanced security systems, modern materials and construction methods ensure the functionality and safety of the building.

Energy Efficiency: Glass facades allow for more natural light and reduce electricity consumption.

Conclusion

The Public Services Center building in Minneapolis is organized at a high functional and aesthetic level, based on modern architectural principles. Building typology - belongs to the category of public buildings intended for the provision of public services, and its functional structure, divided into floors, combines effective service and administrative management.

The skyscraper shape of the building and the use of aluminum and glass materials reflect modernity and correspond to the urban environment. Light and air-oriented design creates a comfortable, humane work environment for employees and citizens. The building is closely connected with the city's infrastructure, and its integration with surrounding vehicles and public spaces increases its territorial significance.

At the same time, the building is environmentally friendly, positively influencing the life of the city through visual connections between internal and external spaces. This creates the basis for considering the building of the Center for Public Services not only as an architectural object, but also as an important part of the city's infrastructure.

In general, the architecture of the building ensures high efficiency in terms of its functionality, integration into the urban environment, and harmony with modern technologies, and plays an important role in providing quality public services to the city's population.

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